

IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF BLDC MOTOR DRIVE BY PID, FUZZY AND ANFIS CONTROLLER

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ABSTRACT:

This article presents the design and simulation of the ANFIS controller for better performance of the servomotor of a brushless DC motor (BLDC). Productivity BLDC servomotors based on ANFIS, fuzzy and PID controller are tested under different operating conditions, for example, changes in speed setting, parameter variations, load disturbance, etc. BLDC servo motors are used in the aerospace, control and measurement systems, electric vehicles, robotics and industrial control applications. In such cases, they are realized, as conventional P, PI and PID controllers of the control systems BLDC drive servo motors satisfactory transient and steady state responses. However, the main problem that arises with a conventional PID controller is that the parameters adjusted gain obtained from the drive control systems of the BLDC servo motor cannot produce a more transient response and a stable state under various operating conditions such as parameter variations, load disturbance, etc. In this Paper, design and implementation of the ANFIS controller and its performance compared to the PID controller and fuzzy controller to show its ability to monitor the errors and utility of ANFIS controller management applications.

KEYWORDS: Brushless DC (BLDC) motor, PID controller, Fuzzy logic controller, ANFIS controller.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Brushless DC Motors (BLDC) motors are widely used in the air transportation, electrical and almost all food and chemical industries. Conventional controllers, such as P, PI and PID, which is used to control the application for more than a couple of decades. This is the key to the development of the appropriate mathematical model, which is a method to simulate real-life situations using mathematical equations to predict their future behavior of any system or reaction system for the presentation of these controllers, but in applications Pragmatic aspects of nonlinear and complex systems; Therefore, they approach as direct systems to obtain a mathematical model. A controller for such systems may simply provide

satisfactory reaction and stable transition, reaction, but not the optimal response. In the vast majority of literary studies it was assumed that the parameters of the system will never show signs of changes in operating conditions, but in the parameters of the pragmatic application of mechanical stress, such as peace and friction can change due to inactivity or decoupling of the clutch components and load changes. The servo BLDC phase resistance may also vary slightly due to the variation of the terminal resistance of the wiring resistance and the semiconductor resistance due to temperature changes in the operating conditions. It was found that the ratio of the contactless battery at full load is 1:15, and the change in the instantaneous image delay is 10-20 times of the delay components for the decoupling or regular movement of automation control and the Positioning of basic weakness of the conventional controllers is that they can give a better transient and consistent state response when the parameters of the system for which they are planned are kept unchanged. In large part, the sensitive system of the parameters of the systems is changed during the operation. The realization of these controllers and their rationality for a wide range of servo motor drive BLDC studied under different operating conditions, such as changing the species of reference speed parameters and load influencing disturbing. The information regarding the various literary material for the purposes of this study as follows.

BLDC motor modeling, evaluation and control of network access evaluation [1] - [4]. The effect of the Change in Motor Parameters on the Performance of the BLDC Drive System is discussed in [6], [7] various fit Methods for the PID SE Controllers Description in [7] - [8]. The design, implementation and Performance Analysis of Fuzzy Logic Controllers (FLC) for divers APPLICATIONS such as the dc servo motor, BLDC motor, gas turbine, servo systems and so on are presented in [5] Design and implementation of adaptive controllers for the management and control of access to the network.

This article consists of six sections. In Section II, the simulation of the BLDC servomotor is presented; Section III describes the development and implementation of the PID regulator; Section IV, the development and

implementation of fuzzy controller are presented, the design and implementation of the ANFIS controller are described; Section V and the final conclusion are presented in Section VI.

II. MODELING OF BLDC SERVOMOTOR DRIVE SYSTEM:

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit of the BLDC servomotor drives system.

BLDC servo motor system, consisting of BLDC servo motor and IGBT inverter modeling [1] - [4] based on assumptions that all stator phase windings have an equal resistance per phase; I permanent and mutual inductance; Power semiconductors are ideal; Insignificant loss of iron; And the engine is not saturated. BLDC equivalent servo system is shown in Figure 1.

The line to line voltage equations are expressed in matrix form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{ab} \\ V_{bc} \\ V_{ca} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R & -R & 0 \\ 0 & R & -R \\ -R & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L & -M & 0 \\ 0 & L & -M \\ M & -L & L \end{bmatrix} \frac{di}{dt} + \begin{bmatrix} e_a - e_b \\ e_b - e_c \\ e_c - e_a \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Since the mutual inductance is negligible as compared to the self-inductance, the aforementioned matrix equation can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{ab} \\ V_{bc} \\ V_{ca} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R & -R & 0 \\ 0 & R & -R \\ -R & 0 & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L & -L \\ -L & 0 & L \end{bmatrix} \frac{di}{dt} + \begin{bmatrix} e_a - e_b \\ e_b - e_c \\ e_c - e_a \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where L and M are self-inductance and mutual inductance per phase; R is the stator winding resistance per phase; ea, eb, and ec are the back EMFs of phases a, b, and c, respectively; ia, ib, and ic are the phase currents of phases a, b, and c, respectively. The electromagnetic torque developed by the motor can be expressed as

$$Te = (ea ia + eb ib + ec ic) / \omega = Kt \omega \quad (3)$$

Where ia = ib = ic = Iω is the angular velocity in radians per second, and Kt is the torque constant.

Since this electromagnetic torque is utilized to overcome the opposing torques of inertia and load, it can also be written as

$$Te = TL + JM d\omega / dt + BM \omega \quad (4)$$

Where TL is the load torque, JM is the inertia, and BM is the friction constant of the BLDC servomotor.

The load torque can be expressed in terms of load inertia JL and friction BL components as

$$TL = JL * d\omega / dt + BL \omega \quad (5)$$

The output power developed by the motor is

$$P = Te \omega \quad (6)$$

$$E = ea = eb = ec = Kb \omega \quad (7)$$

Where Kb is back EMF constant, E is back emf per phase, and ω is the angular velocity in radians per second.

Parameters that change during the operating conditions of R, JM, JL, BE and BL. These parameters can affect the response speed of the BLDC servo motor drive system. Increasing the value of the energy inertia storage elements and JM JL increases the response time setting time or vice versa. Reducing the values of friction components consume the power of the BM and BL to increase the deceleration time response rate or vice versa. Another parameter that is likely to change during working conditions is the phase of the resistance of the BLDC servo motor due to the addition of terminal resistance, phase winding resistance variation and changes in the resistance state of the IGBT switches due to temperature changes. A change in the phase of the resistance can also affect the system speed of the BLDC servo drive servo motor. The mixed combination of inertia, friction and phase resistance of the BLDC servo motor can lead to large slips that are undesirable in most control applications. Therefore, the drive system of the BLDC servo motor requires the appropriate drivers like PID, Fuzzy or ANFIS controllers to speed up the response, reduce overshoot and the steady-state errors do not meet the application requirements. In this work, the BLDC servo motor based on the PID, Fuzzy and ANFIS controller and its operation is investigated in various operating conditions, such a change in the pitch at the initial speed, various system parameters and abrupt load disruptions develop.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the experimental setup.

A block diagram of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. The experimental system consists of four main components. This servo IGBT-power device BLDC inverter motor with load, speed, phase voltage and phase

current and DSP measurement circuits. BLDC servo motor with electronic motor switching. Embedded three Hall sensors generate a signal depending on the position of the rotor. These signals are decoded to identify the position of the rotor and activate respective coil by switching the corresponding IGBT-converter switches. The Hall effect sensors used as inputs for the DSP through an IC buffer. Trigger signals generated by DSP for IGBT-switches also apply to the IC buffer.

The PWM control method is used to control the voltage supplied to the winding to control the speed of the motor. The 20 kHz PWM signal is selected because there is no acoustic noise during engine operation. The duty cycle of the 20 kHz signal generated by the DSP changes to monitor the average current and the average voltage of the phase windings, and thus the torque generated by the motor. The operating cycle of the device is adjusted depending on the output signal. DC output The F signal of the V / V converter is set as one input to the DSP's A / D converter (ADC) to determine the actual motor speed. The speed reference is set using the potentiometer and the repeater voltage and is set as another ADC input signal to determine the reference speed. The function of the DSP processor is to calculate the error and change errors, store these values, calculate the sliding mode output of the controller, define a new cycle for the switching devices and perform electronic switching. PWM signals are generated to switch IGBT devices using components such as the EVA timer module, PWM channels, etc.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF PID CONTROLLER:

Proportional-integral-derived controllers are widely used in industrial control systems, as they require only a few parameters to adjust. PID controllers have the ability to eliminate constant error due to integral action and can anticipate changes in production due to derivative action when the system is exposed to a reference input signal. The most popular method is the calculation of the Ziegler-Nichols PID, which is based only on the parameters obtained from the response to the system stage. A block diagram of an experimental apparatus used to implement the controller is shown in Figure 2. The continuous control signal $u(t)$ of the PID controller is given by

$$u(t) = K_p (e(t) + (1/T_i) \int e(t) dt + T_d de(t)/dt) \quad \dots (8)$$

where, K_p is the proportional gain, T_i is the integral time constant, T_d is the derivative time constant, and $e(t)$ is the error signal.

$$u(k) = u(k-1) + K_1 \times e(k) + K_2 \times e(k-1) + K_3 \times e(k-2) \quad \dots (9)$$

Where $u(k-1)$ is the previous control output, $e(k-1)$ is the previous error, and $e(k-2)$ is the error preceding $e(k-1)$. The constants K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 are given by

$$K_1 = K_p + TK_i/2 + K_d/T \quad \dots (10)$$

$$K_2 = -K_p - 2K_d/T + TK_i/2 \quad \dots (11)$$

$$K_3 = K_d/T \quad \dots (12)$$

$$K_i = K_p / T_i \quad \dots (13)$$

$$K_d = K_p T_d \quad \dots (14)$$

$$T = 1/f \quad \dots (15)$$

Where f is the sampling frequency and T is the sampling rate.

IV. FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER:

Fuzzy logic is a type of estimated number of reasons that evaluate the reality of variables can be any genuine numbers around 0 and 1. For differentiation, the logic of the Boolean, the estimation of the reality of variables can be 0 or 1. The diffuse cause was stretched to cope with the idea of half-truth where the quality Reality can range from completely genuine and completely false. In addition, when using etymological variables, these varieties can be controlled with specific capabilities. Generally, under rational control, it is executed from four fuzzy components displayed in the fuzzification interface of the rice, the fuzzy principle of the induction motor and the network interface of the defuzzification. Each of the parties together with the basic operations of fuzzy logic will be described in more detail below.

Fig.3 Block diagram of a fuzzy inference system.

- It is possible to describe the research strategy and diffuse control study, shown in Figure 3
- Obtain one or more extended assessments or other assessment of conditions in a system, which will be dissolved or checked.
- Treatment of input data according to fuzzy "assuming then" rules that can be transferred to the main page dialect words and combined with the usual non-diffuse formation.
- The means and weighting of the results of all the individual principles in the selection or choice of an output, in which is selected what to do or advise controlled system what to do. The output signal of the result - is an accurate de-fuzzified system. First, the different levels of performance (high speed, low speed, and so on) of the platform is determined by establishing membership functions of the fuzzy sets.

Fuzzy inference system and calculation of back propagation. For a normal fuzzy inference, the parameters about participation opportunities are usually controlled by experience or experimental technique. The system of neuro-fuzzy adaptive induction can overcome this load across the road to detect how to adapt the information participant's information capabilities/output, taking into account the ultimate goal of representing such varieties in data values - automatically selects parameters relevant to the specific work registration. This strategy also works by studying neural systems.

V. ADAPTIVE NEURO-FUZZY INFERENCE SYSTEMS (ANFIS):

Adaptive system of neuro-fuzzy inference (ANFIS) refers in general to an adaptation network that performs the function of the system of inference fuzzy. The most commonly used ANFIS fuzzy system architecture model is Sugeno since it is less computational and more transparent than other models. The serial membership function of the model (MF) Sugeno can be parameterized by any arbitrary function of neat entries is likely polynomial. Polynomials of zero and first order are used as the constant and near linear models of Sugeno, respectively. In addition in the process of defuzzification, Sugeno diffuse model is a simple calculation of the weighted average. Fuzzy space is divided by partition grid according to the preceding number MF, and each diffuse area covered by the rule. On the other hand, each fixed and adaptive network node performs a single function or a sub-Sugeno model, so that the overall performance of the network is functionally the same as that of the diffuse model. The network uses an adaptive optimization algorithm to change the parameters of the fuzzy inference system. The adaptation process is aimed at obtaining a set of parameters for which it minimizes the error between the actual output of the diffuse model and the established target of training data. You can use classic optimization techniques such as backward propagation as well as hybrid algorithms. The total number of modifiable ANFIS parameters is the important computational effort required to complete the tuning process. ANFIS combines the advantages of fuzzy systems and adaptive networks into a hybrid intellectual paradigm. Systems of flexibility and subjectivity with fuzzy inference when added to the optimization of the power of adaptive networks provide a remarkable resistance Amphism simulation, training, nonlinear assignment and pattern recognition.

VI. RESULTS AND CONCLUSION:

A. RESULTS:

The experimental results obtained for BLDC servomotor drive under different operating conditions such as step change in reference speed, different inertia of

the system, different phase resistance of the BLDC servomotor, and with load disturbance are done and below figure show the results with PID, Fuzzy and ANFIS controller.

Below figure shows output of BLDC servomotor by connecting the PID controller. When load is connected to motor at that time speed of motor decreases, because of PID controller after some time period speed come to it's original value.

Fig. 4 Output of BLDC drive by Using PID Controller While we apply the Fuzzy controller on place of PID controller and load is connected to motor then settling time of motor is reduced. That is time required to come motor at its original state when Fuzzy controller is connected is less as compare to PID is less. Below figure shows all outputs of Fuzzy controller.

Fig. 5. Electromotive force of Fuzzy controller

Fig. 6. Stator current of Fuzzy controller

Fig. 7. Electromagnetic torque fuzzy controller

Fig. 8. Reference speed of fuzzy and ANFIS controller

After seeing all parameters of fuzzy controller now below figures shows all the parameters such as electromotive force, stator current, electromagnetic torque, reference speed, actual speed output, error in speed, duty ratio and line to line voltage of ANFIS controller

Fig. 13. Stator current of ANFIS controller

Fig. 9. Actual speed output of fuzzy controller

Fig. 10. Error in speed of Fuzzy Controller

Above figure shows output of error in speed of fuzzy controller. When sudden load is applied to motor speed of motor changes and this speed comes to its original position after some time this setting time is reduced by fuzzy controller

Fig. 11. Duty Ratio of fuzzy controller

Fig. 12. Line to line voltage of fuzzy controller

Fig. 14. Electromotive force of ANFIS controller

Fig. 15. Electromagnetic torque ANFIS controller

Fig. 16. Actual speed output of ANFIS controller

Fig. 17. Error in speed of ANFIS Controller

Above figure shows output of error in speed of fuzzy controller. When sudden load is applied to motor speed of motor changes and this speed comes to it's original position after some time this settling time is reduced by ANFIS controller.

Fig. 18. Duty Ratio of ANFIS controller

Fig. 19. Line to line voltage of ANFIS controller

Fig. 20(a).Output of BLDC drive by Using Fuzzy and ANFIS controller

Finally in this paper we have to compare the output of ANFIS controller with Fuzzy controller. The ANFIS controller gives more accuracy and effective out than Fuzzy and PID controller, below figure shows the comparison of Fuzzy controller and ANFIS controller by connecting to the BLDC motor drive.

Fig. 20 (b).Output of BLDC drive by Using Fuzzy and ANFIS controller

B. CONCLUSION:

PID method and Fuzzy control Anfis has been successfully implemented for the servo motor drive system BLDC. The effect of changing parameters in the performance of the BLDC servo motor drive system has been studied with experimental results. However, the response speed of the BKEPT servo drive based on the fuzzy controller is better than the response speed of the servo motor based on the BLDC PID controller and the response speed of the BLDC servo motor based on the ANFIS controller is better than the PID response speed and fuzzy controller, thus the BLDC PID controller Does not provide improved low variations in system performance parameters. However, the experimental results clearly show that the BLDC servo motor based on the fuzzy controller and ANFIS can provide an improved reaction rate in sequence with the same rise time and there will be a stabilization time when the system is under the load of perturbations, the variation of the parameter and the pitch of the change in the initial speed. Since the ANFIS control system is easy to design and implement effective to cope with uncertainty and parameter changes and has better overall performance, the BLDC servo motor drive system based on the ANFIS controller on the PDC-based BLDC servo motor and the fuzzy controller may be preferred. Automation, robotics control systems and the position of speed and industrial control of applications.

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REFERENCES:

- 1) R. Shanmugasundram, K. Muhammad Zakariah, and N. Yadaiah, 'Implementation and performance analysis of digital controllers for brushless dc motor drives', vol. 19, pp. 213-224, Feb 2014.
- 2) R. Krishnan, *Permanent Magnet Synchronous and Brushless DC Motor Drives: Theory, Operation, Performance, Modeling, Simulation, Analysis, and Design-Part 3, Permanent Magnet Brushless DCMachines and their Control*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2009, pp. 451-563.
- 3) P. Pillay and R. Krishnan, "Modeling, simulation, and analysis of permanent-magnet motor drives, part ii: The brushless dc motor drive," IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl., vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 274-279, Mar./Apr. 1989.
- 4) R. Shanmugasundram, K. M. Zakariah, and N. Yadaiah, "Low-cost high performance brushless dc motor drive for speed control applications," in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Adv. Recent Technol. Commun. Comput., Kottayam, India, Oct. 27-28, 2009, pp. 456-460.

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- 5) R. Shanmugasundram, K. M. Zakariah, and N. Yadaiah, "Digital implementation of fuzzy logic controller for wide range speed control of brushless dc motor," in Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Veh. Electron. Safety, Pune, India, Nov. 10–12, 2009, pp. 119–124.
- 6) A. K. Wallace and R. Spee, "The effects of motor parameters on the performance of brushless dc drives," IEEE Trans. Power Electron., vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 2–8, Jan. 1990.
- 7) V. M. Varatharaju, B. L. Mathur, and K. Udhyakumar, "Speed control of PMSM motor using MATLAB/Simulink and effects of load and inertia changes," in Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Mech. Electr. Technol., Sep. 10–12, 2010, pp. 543–548.
- 8) Q. Wang, T. Lee, H. Fung, Q. Bi, and Y. Zhang, "PID tuning for improved performance," IEEE Trans. Contr. Syst. Technol., vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 457–465, Jul. 1999.
- 9) C. Kala Krishna, Dr. G. V. Marutheswar, "The improved performance of the brushless DC motor driven by using ANFIS Controller" IJIRSET vol. 5 Issue 11, pp. 19641-19647, Nov. 2016.

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